

Study of Dry Eye in Patients of Diabetes Mellitus at Tertiary Care Hospital**Rachana Mandli¹, Mona Deshmukh²**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Dr. Kiran C Patel Medical College & Research Institute, Bharuch, Gujarat, India²DNB Consultant, Mahatma Eye Bank Eye Hospital, Nagpur

Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 26-10-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Diabetes is a major public health concern maximum number in Southeast Asian countries. It was better characterized the relationship with dry eye disease (DED) and ocular surface disorders. This study was conducted to evaluate dry eye disease in diabetic person of 5 or more than 5 years of duration.**Materials & Methods:** 124 diabetic (both type I & Type II DM) male & female patients with age 40 years and above with 5 or >5 years history included in the study. Patients were not considered for study who were on any ocular medications or other systemic illness. Detailed history and general examinations were performed. Patients were divided in four groups based on duration of DM, like 5 to 10 years, 11 to 15 years, 16 to 20 years & 21 to 25 years. Dry eye was graded as mild, moderate and severe. Data was collected and analysed by SPSS software.**Results:** Male diabetics had more prevalence of dry eye than females. Mild dry eye was present among 36.3% of subjects, 29.8% of the subjects had moderate dry eye and only 4.8% had severe dry eye. As duration of Diabetes increased, the percentage of dry eye also increased.**Conclusion:** With increasing duration of Diabetes, the percentage of dry eye also increased, though the difference was found to be statistically insignificant. As per gender, male had more prevalence of dry eye than females. The difference was found to be statistically non-significant.

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Introduction

At present, Diabetes is a major public health concern maximum number in Southeast Asian countries. [1,2] India leads the world in diabetic population and 77.2 million with pre diabetes group and estimated to have 62.4 million people with diabetes group includes controlled DM or uncontrolled DM [3]. By 2030 DM may be affect up to 79.4 million population in India. So, by WHO has labelled India as the diabetic capital of the world. [4] In India the prevalence of DM in adults is 2.3% and 4.0 - 11.6% in the rural and urban population respectively [5] The Dry Eye Workshop (DEWS) (2007) defined dry eye as "a multi factorial disease of the tears and ocular surface diseases that results in symptoms like ocular discomfort, disturbance in vision, and tear film instability (TFI). It is accompanied by increased osmolality of the tear film and inflammation of the ocular surface." ocular surface diseases are common and significantly affects quality of life. [6]

Diabetes with aging are probably the major risk factors responsible for ocular diseases [7-8]. In the last fifteen years besides the commonly known complications, like cataract and diabetic retinopathy, it was better characterized the

relationship with dry eye disease (DED) and ocular surface disorders. Several clinical studies have demonstrated that people with DM are more vulnerable to dry eye than healthy subjects. Normal ocular surface is essential for retinal image quality Due to impact of DM in the ocular surface and the fact that maintaining a, any changes in tear film with DM have been studied in detail over the recent decades. Some ocular manifestations of DM are associated with lacrimal gland dysfunction and have been related to dry eye [9-11].

As per above scenario, this study was conducted to evaluate dry eye disease in diabetic person of 5 or more than 5 years of duration.

Materials & Methods

This study was ethically approved and conducted at tertiary care hospital. Total 124 diabetic (both type I & Type II DM) male & female patients with age 40 years and above with 5 or >5 years history included in the study. Patients were not considered for study who were using anti glaucoma and topical steroid, on oral treatment like Beta blockers anti-hypertensives, antihistaminics, Anti-psycotics, underwent ocular surgery within past 3 month.

Associated with any other known systemic illness like {thyroid, collagen vascular disease, immunological disorders, lid diseases like ectropion, entropion, lagophthalmos, Previous treatment of dry eye taken.

Detailed history and general examinations were performed. Patients were divided in four groups based on duration of DM, like 5 to 10 years, 11 to 15 years, 16 to 20 years & 21 to 25 years. Dry eye was defined as having one more symptom (often or all the time present) along with one or more

positive clinical findings (based on slit lamp examination) and one or more positive clinical tests (tear break up time of ≤ 10 seconds, Schirmer's test score ≤ 10 mm, with anesthesia ≤ 5 mm, fluorescein score of ≥ 1 [12]. Asymptomatic patients with positive signs or positive tests were also considered in the diagnosis. Dry eye was graded as mild, moderate and severe [12]. Data was collected and analysed by SPSS software, P value < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Observations & Results:

Table 1: Distribution of study subjects based on duration of diabetes

Duration of Diabetes	No. of Patients	Percentage
5 – 10 years	92	74.2
11 – 15 years	24	19.4
16 – 20 years	4	3.2
21 – 25 years	4	3.2
Total	124	100 %

Table 2: Prevalence of dry eyes among diabetics based on gender

Gender	Dry eye	
	Present N (%)	Absent N (%)
Male	63 [60.2]	16 [76.2]
Female	41 [39.8]	5 [23.8]
Total	103 [100]	21 [100]
Chi square	1.9	
Degree of freedom	1	
P value	0.21	

Table 3: Prevalence of dry eye based on duration of diabetes

Duration of Diabetes	Dry eye		Total (%)
	Present N (%)	Absent N (%)	
5 – 10 years	73 [79.3]	19 [20.7]	92 [100]
11 – 15 years	23 [95.8]	1 [4.2]	24 [100]
16 – 20 years	4 [100]	0	4 [100]
21 – 25 years	3 [75]	1 [25]	4 [100]
Chi square	4.6		
Degree of freedom	3		
P value	0.09		

Table 4: Severity of dry eyes among diabetic subjects

Eyes condition among Diabetics	Number	Percentage (%)
Normal eyes	36	29
Mild dry eyes	45	36.3
Moderate dry eyes	37	29.8
Severe dry eyes	6	4.8

Results

Table 1 shows that maximum diabetic patients [74.2%] involved in our research had the duration of diabetes in the range of 5-10 years.

Least no. of patients had duration above 15 years [3.2%]. Table 2 shows male had more prevalence of dry eye than females. Though the difference was found statistically non-significant. Table 3 shows no. of years of duration of Diabetes increased, the

percentage of dry eye also increased, though the difference was found to be statistically insignificant. Table 4 shows mild dry eye was present among 36.3% of subjects, 29.8% of the subjects had moderate dry eye and only 4.8% had severe dry eye.

Discussion

In our study we included patients of diabetes mellitus type 1 and type 2 with duration of diabetes

on treatment was more than 5 year (Table 1). In diabetic group among male and female (Table 2), prevalence of dry eye was more in male as compared to females. Though the difference was found statistically non-significant (p value=0.21). Similar results were found in studies like Manaviat et al, (p value =0.2), Hasan et al (p value 0.733 and OR=1.15), Pakalapati et al (p value>0.05 and OR 1.02), Yoon et al, Kaiserman et al, Burda N et al, Najafi et al, Fuerst et al, Elsaadani et al, Ribeiro et al, Aljarousha et al (p value>0.05) [12-22]. while Moss et al found 16.7% incidence of dry eyes in diabetic women compared to 11.4% in diabetic men with statistically significant correlation of gender (p value less than 0.001). Females had more prevalence of dry eye as compared to males. [23]

According to Table 3, dry eye prevalence increased with increasing duration of diabetes but there was no statistical correlation significance noted (p=0.09). This finding was not consistent with studies conducted by Ozdemir et al (p>0.05), Yoon et al, Hasan et al, Pakalapati et al, Manaviat et al While study by Yash Hada et Al found a significant association between duration of diabetes and frequency of dry eye syndrome (p=0.01) [12-14,24-26]. Total 32.31% showed dry eye prevalence increase with duration more than 5 year.

In our study (Table 4), the diabetic patients, mild dry eye was present among 36.3% of eyes and 29.8% of the eyes had moderate dry eye. On statistically analysing the severity of dry eyes among diabetics and non-diabetics, no statistical significance was observed between the various degrees of dry eye severity between two groups and the three tests. Similar results were postulated by Yoon et al, Burda et al, Fuerst N et al and Hasan et al [12,17,27,25].

Conclusion

In this study, it was found that with increasing duration of Diabetes, the percentage of dry eye also increased, though the difference was found to be statistically insignificant. As per gender, male had more prevalence of dry eye than females. The difference was found to be statistically non-significant.

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